

QUIZ**LAST NAME: NGULUBE****FIRST NAME: MOSES****PROGRAM CODE : DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: Word 2019 on Mac

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Kindly select the correct list of illustrative plagiaristic acts from the four options below:**

- Parenthetical citation, collusion, paraphrasing, copying and pasting
- Verbatim, in-text citation, paraphrasing and collusion
- Using third parties to write assignments, collusion, verbatim, copying, and pasting.¹**
- Auto-plagiarism, verbatim, parenthetical referencing, and paraphrasing

2. **How would you describe a conceptual question?**

¹ University of Oxford, "Plagiarism," Oxford Students, 2020, accessed August 14th, 2020, <https://www.ox.ac.uk/students/academic/guidance/skills/plagiarism>.

- It is a question whose answer to the 'so what?' does not tell readers what to do but helps them to understand an issue under study.²
- It is a question that helps readers to think about what to do in preventing fallacious claims.
- It is a question that guides readers to know what to do in real life.
- It is a question that is only answered by professors developing new conceptual frameworks.

3. **What is a research hypothesis?**

- It is a detailed description of a study problem.
- It is a critical review of published literature on the research topic.
- It is a collection of research recommendations to implement study findings.
- It is a tentative answer to a research problem to guide research.³

4. **What sources can one omit from a bibliography?**

- Journal and newspaper articles; the Bible and other sacred books, major dictionaries and encyclopedias.

² Kate Turabian L, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers, 8th Edition*, edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16.

³ Ibid, 13.

- Classical and medieval literary works, the US Constitution, legal cases and newspaper articles⁴**
 - Unpublished interviews and personal communication; and scientific journal articles
 - Major encyclopedia, legal cases and new books by young authors
5. **What are the main philosophical assumptions that a qualitative researcher needs to consider?**
- Metaphysical, axiological, and epistemological.
 - Epistemological, cosmological, and ontological
 - Ontological, epistemological, and axiological⁵**
 - Logical positivism, ontological, and metaphysical
6. **What are some of the key paradigms of qualitative research?**
- Social constructivism, interpretivism, or naturalistic inquiry⁶**
 - Post-positivism, interpretivism, and critical theory
 - Pragmatism, interpretivism, and empirical inquiry
 - Critical advocacy, post-positivism, and social constructivism
7. **Please select the correct list of illustrative forms of qualitative research:**

⁴ Turabian, 95, 132–33.

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 8.

⁶ *Ibid*, 9–10.

- Randomized control trials, case study, and ethnography
 - Hermeneutics, textual analysis, and polling
 - Phenomenology, case study, and textual analysis**⁷
 - Narrative research, experimental research, and grounded theory
8. **What are the critical global summits between 1970 and 2014 that influenced the global discourse regarding sustainable development?**
- Stockholm 1972; Rio 1992; Beijing 1995, and Johannesburg 2002.
 - Stockholm 1972; Rio 1992; Johannesburg 2002, and Rio 2012.**⁸
 - Stockholm 1972; Rio 1992; Maputo 2003, and Rio 2012.
 - Stockholm 1972; Rio 1992, Abuja 2000, and Johannesburg 2002.
9. **What are the main categories around which sustainable development is framed within Agenda 21?**
- Political, philosophical, and economic
 - Social, ecological, and phenomenological
 - Environmental, social, and political
 - Economic, social, and environmental**⁹

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 10.

⁸ Tchigankong Noubissie, "The Concept of Sustainable Development and Sustainable Management of Natural Resources in Africa through the German Development Cooperation. Case Study: Benin, Cameroon and Namibia (PhD diss., University of Giessen, 2012), 5–6.

⁹ Ibid, 117.

10. **Kindly select the correct list of three key concepts that Wenham (2015) used in her doctoral dissertation to discuss global disease governance:**

- Sovereignty, responsibility, and governance¹⁰**
- Vaccination, responsibility, and governance
- Quarantine, sovereignty, and responsibility
- Lock-down, responsibility, and governance

¹⁰ Clare Wenham, "Examining Sovereignty in Global Disease Governance: Surveillance Practices in United Kingdom, Thailand and Lao People's Democratic Republic" (PhD diss., Aberystwyth University, 2015), 21.

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